

1 **Fire and land use impact soil properties in a Mediterranean dry sclerophyll woodland**

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8 **Abstract**

9 Fire directly impacts soil properties responsible for soil function and can result in soil
10 degradation. Across the globe, climate change-induced droughts and elevated temperatures
11 are exacerbating fire regime severity, breadth, and frequency, thus posing a threat to soil
12 function and dependent ecosystem services. In Australia, the 2019-2020 fire season
13 consumed nearly 50% of Kangaroo Island, South Australia, burning both dry sclerophyll
14 woodland and adjacent historically cleared and grazed pastureland. Due to exacerbated fire
15 regime elements, e.g., intensity and area affected, and interactions with historical land use,
16 post-fire recovery of soil function was uncertain. This study assessed the impacts of a) the
17 2019-2020 fire event in Western River, Kangaroo Island on dry sclerophyll woodland and b)
18 the interaction between this fire event and historical clearing and grazing on post-fire
19 function of the soil. To do so, the following physicochemical and biological soil properties
20 were analysed: labile active carbon, total carbon, total nitrogen, carbon to nitrogen ratio
21 (C/N), pH, electrical conductivity, soil water repellency, aggregate stability, microbial
22 community composition, and microbial diversity. Our results showed that the fire was of high
23 severity, causing a reduction in nutrient content, an extreme rise in pH, and significant

24 modifications to fungal communities in burnt compared to unburnt dry sclerophyll woodland.
25 Furthermore, clearing and grazing raised post-fire soil nutrient levels and soil microbial
26 diversity but reduced soil C/N and the abundance of ectomycorrhizal fungi in burnt
27 pastureland compared to burnt woodland soils. This study highlights the role of management
28 and fire severity in post-fire outcomes and emphasizes the need for comprehensive soil
29 function assessments to evaluate the impacts of disturbance on soil. Taking direct measure of
30 soil properties, as done here, will improve future assessments of fire season impacts and post-
31 fire recovery in fire-prone landscapes.

32 **1. Introduction**

33 Climate change-exacerbated fire regimes and land use change are two prominent global
34 factors that are capable of land degradation, which results from loss of soil function (Neary,
35 2009; Rovira et al., 2004). In consequence, land degradation threatens a plethora of soil
36 dependent ecosystem services, e.g., agricultural and natural productivity, biodiversity and
37 habitat, soil carbon sequestration and storage, air and water filtration, and hydrological
38 cycling (Bateman and Muñoz-Rojas, 2019; IRP, 2019; Shakesby and Doerr, 2006). While
39 fires and human land use have impacted soils for millennia, temperature rise and drought
40 associated with climate change have caused longer and drier fire seasons, resulting in higher
41 frequency, intensity and severity of fires in the Mediterranean landscape (Jolly et al., 2015;
42 Nolan et al., 2020). In combination with land use, changes to these elements of the fire
43 regime raise the likelihood of fire-induced land degradation on both managed and non-
44 managed lands.

45 Australia is an example of a particularly fire-prone country (Nolan et al., 2020). Fire in
46 Mediterranean eucalypt forests has been shown to increase soil nutrient content, electrical
47 conductivity (EC) and pH in soils immediately post-fire (Christensen and Abbott, 1989;
48 Etchells et al., 2020; Hopmans et al., 2005; Krishnaraj et al., 2016; Polglase et al., 1986).

49 These changes can promote seedling and resprout growth, and properties of fire, such as heat,
50 can cue and promote the germination of many plant species in fire prone ecosystems (Palmer
51 et al., 2018) and can stimulate soil microbial activity (Bárceñas-Moreno et al., 2016; Wang et
52 al., 2015). Subsequently, variation in heat and other properties related to the fire regime
53 drives diversity in the community composition of soil microbes and plants (Fultz et al., 2016;
54 Nolan et al., 2021). In these ways, fire can promote positive outcomes on Mediterranean dry
55 sclerophyll woodlands. However, climate change-induced temperature rise and drought can
56 push fire-regimes beyond the current limits of fire-prone ecosystems (Collins et al., 2021;
57 Dowdy, 2018; Neary, 2009; Nolan et al., 2021).

58 High severity fire has been shown to reduce soil nutrient content, promote post-fire soil
59 erosion and nutrient runoff, result in tree-kill and mortality of other vegetation, and reduce
60 seed bank size (Neary, 2009; Palmer et al., 2018; Pereira et al., 2019; Rovira et al., 2004).
61 Furthermore, cascading disturbance events have the potential to cause more damage to soil
62 and ecosystems than a single event alone (AghaKouchak et al., 2018; Gill and Malamud,
63 2016; Kemter et al., 2021; Zscheischler et al., 2018). When fire occurs too frequently,
64 changes can include cumulative losses of nutrients and fertility, a state shift in plant
65 community type, and the reduction of carbon storage capacity in the soil and above-ground
66 vegetation (Pellegrini et al., 2018; Rovira et al., 2004). These changes have far-reaching
67 implications for the persistence of species in the affected ecosystem and can promote global
68 warming drivers, reinforcing further ecosystem changes (Staal et al., 2020). In consequence,
69 fire-induced ecosystem degradation in Mediterranean regions is a growing concern in the
70 Australian landscape.

71 Land use change is another factor capable of land degradation through significant changes to
72 soil properties. As of 2011, ~45% of Australia's land was used for grazing livestock on native
73 vegetation, and another 9% had been converted from native vegetation to pastureland, a

74 process which involves clearcutting woodlands before implanting non-native forage crops
75 (Australian Bureau of Agricultural and Resource Economics and Sciences, 2016). It has been
76 shown that intense grazing, particularly in times of drought, can alter soil carbon levels,
77 increase nitrates and ammonium, reduce the soil carbon to nitrogen ratio (C/N), alter pH and
78 microbial respiration, and cause soil compaction and soil erosion (Bell et al., 2011; Drewry,
79 2006; Northup et al., 2005; Yates et al., 2000). Furthermore, clear-cutting can reduce plant
80 biodiversity, soil organic matter (SOM) stability, soil carbon storage capacity and carbon
81 content (Baldock et al., 2013; Miralles et al., 2012; Sangha et al., 2006). The effects of
82 grazing native vegetation can be mediated by increasing time between grazing and decreasing
83 duration of grazing (Northup et al., 2005; Yates et al., 2000). However, for pastureland that
84 has been cleared for grazing, severe alterations to vegetation type have already occurred,
85 imposing long-term consequences on soil microbial community composition and function
86 and other dependent ecosystem services (Hart et al., 2005; Muñoz-Rojas et al., 2016c;
87 Shakesby and Doerr, 2006).

88 In the Australian landscape, raised nitrogen and reduced C/N from clearing and grazing have
89 been shown to promote weeds and stifle revegetation of woodlands (Bui and Henderson,
90 2013; McGregor et al., 2017; Neave and Raison, 1999). Furthermore, reduced plant
91 biodiversity, SOM stability, and soil carbon content from clearcutting are known to inhibit
92 natural revegetation (McGregor et al., 2017). Effective soil management depends on a sound
93 understanding of soil function, and relatively recently, soil management has been focused on
94 restoration of previously disturbed land, such as burnt soils or cleared grazing pastures
95 (Bateman and Muñoz-Rojas, 2019; IRP, 2019). However, the ways in which fire impacts
96 soils in cleared and grazed lands, remain unclear.

97 In response to climate change-induced droughts and elevated temperatures, fires are
98 becoming more extreme in the Australian landscape. The 2019-2020 fire season, colloquially

99 known as the Black Summer fires, reflected a pattern of recent increases in megafires in
100 Australia and around the world (Boer et al., 2020; Le Breton et al., 2022), burning areas at
101 unprecedented scales and impacting both native vegetation and adjoining managed land, e.g.,
102 pastures and cropland. In this study, we aimed to a) evaluate the short-term impacts of a
103 Black Summer bushfire and b) the interactive effects of the fire and historical clearing and
104 grazing on post-fire soil function.

105 Soil properties, including soil organic matter quantity and quality, microbial community
106 composition and respiration rates, and ratios between these properties, are known indicators
107 of soil function (Muñoz-Rojas et al., 2016b; Schimann et al., 2012a). Because of their
108 indicative power and sensitivity to environmental changes, these properties have been used in
109 assessing impacts of disturbances, e.g., mining, logging, and fire, on soils in forested as well
110 as cleared ecosystems (Ammitzboll et al., 2021; Mikita-Barbato et al., 2015; Muñoz-Rojas et
111 al., 2016b; Schimann et al., 2012b).

112 Measuring soil properties directly is a common way of assessing soil health (Francos et al.,
113 2018b; Muñoz-Rojas et al., 2016a). Traditional methods for measuring physicochemical
114 properties are still used today. However, new technologies are being developed and used for
115 assessing microbial soil properties. Culture-dependent methods such as phospholipid fatty
116 acid (PLFA) analysis are common traditional methods for assessing soil microbial
117 community composition and abundance, but recently, Next Generation Sequencing (NGS)
118 has become more affordable and commonly used for studying both bacteria and eukaryote
119 communities (Ammitzboll et al., 2021; Fernandes et al., 2018; Machado De Lima et al.,
120 2021a). Unlike PLFA, which identifies microbial groups present through PLFA biomarkers,
121 NGS identifies DNA sequences, which can be assigned at much deeper group levels, i.e., the
122 operation taxonomic unit (OTU) and Phylum through Genus, compared to PLFA. This allows

123 for more descriptive microbial diversity and relative microbial abundance than would be
124 possible with PLFA and other culture-dependent methods (Peddle et al., 2022).

125 In this study, we directly measured soil physicochemical and biological properties that are
126 known to be affected by fire and land management and/or have been shown to effectively
127 indicate soil function and have been used to assess the impacts of disturbance on soils
128 (Francos et al., 2018a; Fultz et al., 2016; Muñoz-Rojas et al., 2016b; Rovira et al., 2004). We
129 hypothesized that the impacts of clearing and grazing on soil would compound the effects of
130 fire, resulting in signs of accelerated land degradation in burnt pastures compared to burnt
131 woodland.

132 **2. Materials and methods**

133 *2.1 Site description*

134 The study area, located in Western River on the northwest coast of Kangaroo Island, South
135 Australia (35°42'S, 136°53'E – 35°45'S, 137°1'E), has an elevation ranging from 181 to 298
136 meters with a slope ranging from 5 to 48° (9-110%). The area is classified as a Mediterranean
137 climate with warm/cool summers, class Csb in the World Köppen classifications (Peel et al.,
138 2007) and experiences a mean annual rainfall of 553mm and a mean annual temperature
139 ranging from 11.6 to 19.2°C (Commonwealth Australia Bureau of Meteorology, 2022).

140 Predominant soils in the area are made up of loam and sandy loam consisting of ferric brown-
141 red Chromosols and Kurosols and rocky Sodosols and Tenosols (Department for
142 Environment and Water, 2009a, 2009b; DEWNR Soil and Land Program, n.d.).

143 There are both managed and non-managed sites in the study area. Sites referred to as
144 managed were historically cleared and grazed, most likely by sheep, and grazing practices
145 were abandoned after the property was purchased by a new owner in 2008. Non-managed
146 sites consisted of dry sclerophyll woodland with no current nor known historical land use
147 (Fig. 1). In December 2019, a high severity bushfire burned nearly half of Kangaroo Island

148 (2100 km²) including the study site (Bonney et al., 2020). The 2019 fire event was the first
149 fire occurrence in over 60 years, and it affected all managed regions of the study site and
150 most non-managed areas, leaving some long unburnt non-managed areas (Department for
151 Environment and Water, 2020). Dominant plant species included *Eucalyptus baxteri*,
152 *Eucalyptus obliqua*, and *Eucalyptus cladocalyx* in the overstory and *Allocasuarina striata*
153 and *Banksia marginata* in the understory of woodland areas, and three weed species,
154 *Romulea* spp., *Medicago* spp., and *Arctotheca calendula* and the native grass, *Rytidosperma*
155 *geniculatum*, in burnt, cleared pastures (Fig. 1). The non-managed sites can be described as
156 dry sclerophyll or mallee woodland, and from this point on will be referred to as dry
157 sclerophyll woodland.

158

159 **Figure 1.** Study sites. Vegetation at study sites 6-months post-fire for (A) unburnt dry
160 sclerophyll woodland (UNM), (B) burnt dry sclerophyll woodland (BNM), and (C) burnt
161 pastureland (BM). All photos were taken in June 2020 in Western River, South Australia.
162 Photos: Michael Bennell

163 2.2 *Experimental design and soil sampling*

164 Within the study area, we set up 10m x 10m experimental plots across 12 sites with
165 contrasting land uses, i.e., four plots in burnt and grazed pasture (BM), four in burnt dry
166 sclerophyll woodland (BNM), and four in unburnt dry sclerophyll woodland (UNM).
167 Between June and October 2020, two sets of nine soil core samples (20cm diameter) from
168 each plot were collected from the top 5cm of soil at 3m intervals. Once transported to the
169 laboratories at the University of New South Wales (UNSW), one set of soil samples were air
170 dried, sifted through a 2mm sieve, and pooled into three replicate samples per plot (n=36) for
171 physicochemical analysis. The second set of soil samples (n=108) was immediately stored at
172 4°C, and 1g subsamples were stored at -80°C for future DNA analysis.

173 2.3 *Soil physicochemical analyses*

174 Labile active carbon (AC) was determined using a potassium permanganate (KMnO₄)
175 extraction (Weil et al., 2003). 20mL of 0.02M KMnO₄ in 0.1M CaCl₂, adjusted to a pH of
176 7.2, was added to 5g of soil. The solution was placed on an orbital shaker for 2 minutes,
177 allowed to settle for 5-10 minutes, and centrifuged at 1500rpm for 5 minutes. The solution
178 was diluted at a 1:50 ratio in deionized water, and the absorbance was measured by an
179 Epoch2 Microplate Spectrophotometer (BioTek Instruments, VT, USA) at the 550nm
180 wavelength and the absorbance measurement was converted to mg·C/kg·soil (Blair et al.,
181 1995; Fig. S1).

182 Total carbon (TC) and total nitrogen (TN) percentages were measured using a vario MACRO
183 cube (Elementar, Sydney, NSW, Australia) at the Mark Wainwright Analytical Centre
184 (UNSW Sydney). Soil pH and electrical conductivity (EC) were determined from soil diluted
185 in deionized water at a 1:5 ratio using a pH and EC meter, respectively (Instrument Choice,
186 SA, Australia). Soil water repellency (SWR) was determined by measuring the water droplet
187 penetration time (WDPT), the time in seconds required for one droplet of water to reach a

188 contact angle of 0° on oven dried soil, dried overnight at 105°C (Dekker et al., 2001; Ritchie
189 et al., 2020).

190 The Emerson Water Dispersion test (EWDt) was used to analyse soil aggregate stability
191 (AS) (Craze et al., 2003). Two to three soil aggregates per soil sample, 4-8mm in diameter,
192 were handpicked, placed into deionized water, and then each aggregate was classified using
193 Emerson Class numbers at 5 minutes, 2 hours, and 24 hours.

194 *2.4 DNA sequencing and data analyses*

195 For all sub-samples stored at -80°C, rocks, organic matter, and other debris were removed
196 manually, soil samples were pooled into three replicate samples per plot (n=36), and soil
197 aggregates were crushed. Environmental DNA extraction was then carried out on 1g of soil
198 per sample using the DNeasy PowerSoil Pro Kit (QIAGEN, Hilden, Germany) according to
199 the manufacturer's protocol. The obtained DNA products were submitted to the Ramaciotti
200 Centre for Genomics (UNSW, Australia) for amplicon sequencing following their
201 procedures. We targeted the 16S and 18S rRNA genes, which provide information on the
202 diversity (number of phylotypes) and composition (proportion of phylotypes) of bacteria and
203 soil eukaryotes, respectively. Specifically, the V1-V3 region of the 16S rRNA gene was
204 amplified with 27F and 519R primers, and the hypervariable region, V9, of the 18S rDNA
205 was amplified with 1391F and EukB primers. Amplified products were purified and
206 reamplified in a second indexing PCR added with a unique Illumina Nextera XT index for
207 each sample. Paired-end amplicon sequencing was performed on the Illumina MiSeq
208 platform using MiSeq Reagents kit v3 2x150bp Nano. Raw sequencing data was processed
209 with the OTUreporter v1.1.0-beta (28979b8, 16S; 346d8da, 18S) pipeline
210 (<https://bitbucket.org/xvazquezc/otureporter>), based on mothur (v1.39.5,
211 <http://www.mothur.org/>) (Schloss et al., 2009), following the same protocol as Machado De
212 Lima et al. (2021). Taxonomic classification was assigned based on the classification given

213 by SILVA database v132 (Quast et al., 2013). The OptiClust algorithm was used to group
 214 sequences into operational taxonomic units (OTUs) based on 97% similarity using the
 215 OptiClust algorithm (Westcott and Schloss, 2017).

216 First, 16S reads and 18S reads were each subdivided into two data sets, all samples from
 217 burnt sites (B) and all samples from non-managed woodland sites (NM), and these data sets
 218 were subsampled based on the sample with the lowest number of total sequence reads in each
 219 data set, i.e., 12,167 (16S-B), 12,514 (16S-NM), 35,717 (18S-B) and 35,717 (18S-NM).
 220 Sequencing error was assessed using NO SEQ ERROR TEXT as the control in each
 221 sequencing run.

222 Data were rarefied and prepared for alpha diversity analysis using the *phyloseq* R package
 223 (McMurdie and Holmes, 2013). The alpha diversity measures, richness (S), Shannon's
 224 entropy (H), inverse Simpson diversity (D^{-1}), Pielou's (Shannon-Weaver) evenness (J), and
 225 Simpson's evenness (E_D), were then calculated using the *microbiome* R package (Lahti and
 226 Shetty, 2017). Then, the hill numbers, representing the effective number of OTUs (qD) of
 227 each sample, were calculated, averaged across treatment, and plotted against q, a parameter
 228 responsible for the weight given to each OTU based on relative abundance, for $0 \leq q \leq 3$
 229 (Alberdi and Gilbert, 2019; Hill, 1973). qD is given by the following equation:

$$230 \quad {}^qD = \left(\sum_{i=1}^S p_i^q \right)^{1/(1-q)}, q \neq 1 \quad (1)$$

231 When $q = 0$, each OTU is treated equally and qD equals S. When $q = 1$, each OTU is
 232 weighted by its relative abundance and qD approaches the natural exponent of H (e^H). When q
 233 $= 2$, dominant OTUs are overweighted, rare OTUs are underweighted compared to their
 234 respective abundances, and qD equals D^{-1} . (Alberdi and Gilbert, 2019; Hill, 1973)

235 To calculate microbial abundance, OTUs corresponding to the Fungi kingdom were isolated
 236 from 18S OTU reads (43.7% of 18S OTU reads). Then, all OTUs with fewer than 10 reads

237 across all samples were removed from both the 16S and fungi data sets, i.e., 90% of unique
238 OTUs and 10% of all reads and 78% of all OTUs and 2% of all reads, respectively. The rarest
239 classes collectively representing less than or equal to 5% of all OTU reads were grouped and
240 labelled “Other”, and the relative abundance of all classes were plotted by treatment.

241 *2.5 Statistical analyses*

242 Data (Table S1) were tested for normality and homogeneity of variance using the
243 Kolmogorov-Smirnov test and the Levene test, respectively, log-transforming groups of data
244 as needed. Data from each data set, the non-managed data set (UNM vs. BNM) and the burnt
245 data set (BNM vs. BM), were then approximated using mixed models. If data were normal
246 and variances were homogenous, data were modelled using a Generalized Linear Mixed
247 model (GLMM) (*glmmTMB* package) with a Gaussian error distribution (Brooks et al.,
248 2017). Else, a Linear Mixed model (LMM) (*nlme* package) was used with a random error
249 distribution (Pinheiro et al., 2021). The SWR data of non-managed plots and AC data from
250 burnt plots did not meet the assumptions for a linear mixed model, so we modelled the data
251 using a GLMM with a negative binomial error distribution (Bates et al., 2015). All models
252 considered included fire or land treatment as the independent variable and plot number as a
253 random variable. A significance test ($p < 0.5$) of the contrasts of estimated marginal means
254 was then used to identify differences in soil property values due to the treatments, fire (BNM
255 vs. UNM) and land management (BM vs. BNM). All analyses utilized the open-source
256 software R, version 4.0.4 (R Core Team, 2021).

257 **3. Results**

258 *3.1 Soil physicochemical characteristics*

259 There were no significant differences in AC nor EC observed between paired treatments, BM
260 vs. BNM and BNM vs. UNM (Fig. 2A; Fig. 2F; Table S1). Compared to UNM plots, BNM
261 plots had higher pH (6.20 ± 0.06 vs. 4.44 ± 0.08) (Fig. 2E) and lower TC ($3.35 \pm 0.15\%$ vs.

262 $18.85 \pm 2.43\%$), TN ($0.13 \pm 0.01\%$ vs. $0.67 \pm 0.08\%$), and SWR (55 ± 8 vs. 3463 ± 122
263 seconds) (Fig. 2B; Fig. 2C; Fig. 2G), but there was no significant difference in C/N ($26.60 \pm$
264 1.22 vs. 28.43 ± 0.48) (Fig. 2D). Compared to BNM plots, BM plots had higher post-fire TC
265 ($5.86 \pm 0.55\%$) and TN ($0.39 \pm 0.04\%$) (Fig. 2B, Fig. 2C), lower C/N (14.92 ± 0.51) and pH
266 (5.40 ± 0.08) (Fig. 2D; Fig. 2E), and a more variable range of SWR (1064 ± 209 seconds)
267 (Fig. 2G). (Table S1A)

268

269

270 **Figure 2.** Comparisons of soil physicochemical properties by treatment. All soil properties
 271 were measured from samples of the topsoil (0-5cm). (A) Potassium permanganate soluble
 272 organic carbon (AC), (B) total soil carbon (TC), (C) total soil nitrogen (TN), (D)

273 carbon:nitrogen ratio (C/N), (E) soil pH, (F) soil electrical conductivity (EC), and (G) soil
 274 water repellency (SWR). UNM: unburnt non-managed plots; BNM: burnt non-managed
 275 plots; BM: burnt managed plots. Asterisks indicate significant differences due to fire, UNM
 276 vs. BNM, or management, BNM vs. BM, as determined by the contrasts of estimated
 277 marginal means, $p < 0.05$ (*), $p < 0.01$ (**) and $p < 0.001$ (***)).

278 Soil aggregates between 4 and 8mm were found in all non-managed plots (UNM and BNM)
 279 and subsamples, but in one of the four BM plots, there were no aggregates found with a
 280 diameter greater than 4mm. Throughout the EWDT, aggregates trended towards slight
 281 slaking and/or dispersion, but there were no significant differences in the aggregate stability
 282 due to fire nor land management (Fig. 3).

283

284 **Figure 3.** Aggregate stability distribution. Relative abundance of aggregate stability Emerson
 285 Class numbers after 5, 120, and 1440 minutes in water. Class 2: slaking and some dispersion;
 286 Class 7: some swelling and/or slaking but no dispersion; Class 8: no swelling, slaking, or
 287 dispersion. UNM: unburnt non-managed plots; BNM: burnt non-managed plots; BM: burnt
 288 managed plots.

289 3.2 Microbial community composition

290

291 **Figure 4.** Relative microbial abundance. Relative abundance of rRNA gene sequence reads
 292 by treatment and plot site for (A) 16S rRNA bacteria at the phylogenetic class level and (B)
 293 18S rRNA (only fungi are shown, which correspond to 68.5% of assigned soil eukaryote
 294 OTUs) at the order level. UNM: unburnt non-managed plots; BNM: burnt non-managed
 295 plots; BM: burnt managed plots. Other: the rarest OTUs adding up to $\leq 5\%$ of all OTU reads.

296 Both bacterial and soil fungal community compositions varied due to fire treatment and land
 297 management (Fig. 4). Fire reduced the relative abundance (RA) of Acidobacteria, (2.58% vs.
 298 20.58% RA), while increasing the RA of Bacteroidetes, Chloroflexi, and Firmicutes. Land
 299 management caused a rise in Acidobacteria (12.31% vs. 2.58% RA) and Actinobacteria
 300 Thermalleophilia (14.22% vs. 4.33% RA) and a decline in Bacteroidetes (2.32% vs. 6.89%
 301 RA) and Proteobacteria (30.16% vs. 46.67% RA). (Fig. 4A)

302 Basidiomycota, Ascomycota, and Mucoromycota were the dominant fungal groups present in
303 UNM, BNM, and BM plots, respectively, representing 57.7%, 72.01%, and 40.47% RA,
304 respectively. Fire treatment caused a significant decrease in Basidiomycota (9.23% vs. 57.7%
305 RA) and Basidiomycota Agaricomycetes but caused an increase in the abundance of
306 Basidiomycota Tremellomycetes. Fire also raised the abundance of Ascomycota (72.01% vs.
307 27.84% RA) and Ascomycota Dothideomycetes Pleosporales but reduced the RA of
308 Ascomycota Leotiomycetes. Furthermore, fire caused a decrease in Mucoromycota
309 Mortierellales and an increase in Mucoromycota Umbelopsidales. Fire had no impact on the
310 RA of ectomycorrhizal (ECM) fungi containing orders, ~44% in both UNM and BNM plots.
311 However, the RA of three ECM fungi inclusive orders, Basidiomycota Agaricomycetes
312 Cantharalleales, Basidiomycota Agaricomycetes Thelephorales and Ascomycota
313 Leotiomycetes Helotiales, were significantly reduced, while only one order, Ascomycota
314 Eurotiomycetes Eurotiales, increased in RA. (Fig. 4B)

315 Management impacted burnt communities by increasing the RA of Mucoromycota (40.47%
316 vs. 13.22% RA) and decreasing the RA of Mucoromycota Umbelopsidales. Management also
317 increased the RA of Mucoromycota Mortierellales and decreased the RA of Ascomycota
318 Eurotiomycetes Eurotiales, resulting in an overall reduction in the RA of known ECM fungi.
319 Basidiomycota was more abundant due to management, while management had no effect on
320 the RA of Basidiomycota Tremellomycetes. Management also reduced the RA of
321 Ascomycota (34.98% vs. 72.01% RA), but Ascomycota were more abundant than
322 Basidiomycota in both BNM and BM plots. Furthermore, the class distribution of
323 Ascomycota in the BM plots resembled that of BNM plots, consisting of Eurotiomycetes as
324 the dominant class, and a low occurrence of the classes, Dothideomycetes and
325 Leotiomycetes. (Fig. 4B)

327 3.3 Microbial community diversity

328

329 **Figure 5.** Microbial community diversity. Hill numbers and alpha diversity metrics for (A)
 330 bacterial communities of burnt plots (BNM vs. BM), (B) bacterial communities of non-
 331 managed plots (UNM vs. BNM), (C) soil eukaryotes of burnt plots (BNM vs. BM), and (D)
 332 soil eukaryotes of non-managed plots (UNM vs. BNM). Hill numbers (qD) representing the
 333 effective number of OTUs are plotted against the weight of common OTUs, q . qD is equal to
 334 the alpha diversity metrics, richness (S), natural exponent of Shannon's entropy (e^H), and
 335 Inverse Simpson's diversity (D^{-1}), when $q = 0$, $q = 1$, and $q = 2$, respectively. $H/\ln(S)$:
 336 Pielou's evenness (J); D^{-1}/S : Simpson's evenness (E_D). UNM: unburnt non-managed plots;

337 BNM: burnt non-managed plots; BM: burnt managed plots. Asterisks indicate significant
338 differences between treatments, as determined by the contrasts of estimated marginal means,
339 $p < 0.05$ (*), $p < 0.01$ (**) and $p < 0.001$ (***)).

340 The fire caused S, e^H , D^{-1} , J and E_D of bacterial communities to increase in BNM compared
341 to UNM plots (Fig. 5A) but had no effect on the same metrics in soil eukaryote communities
342 (Fig. 5C). Furthermore, clearing and grazing caused an increase in S, e^H and J and a decrease
343 in E_D of bacterial communities in BM compared to BNM plots (Fig. 5B). Clearing and
344 grazing also caused an increase in S, e^H and J of soil eukaryote communities (Fig. 5D) but
345 had no effect on D^{-1} of bacterial communities (Fig. 5B) nor D^{-1} and E_D of soil eukaryote
346 communities (Fig. 5D). (Table S1B; Table S1C)

347 **4. Discussion**

348 Due to fire, burnt dry sclerophyll woodland (BNM) plots underwent complete canopy
349 consumption and significant changes to soil physicochemical and biological properties
350 compared to unburnt dry sclerophyll woodland (UNM) plots. Many of these changes
351 contradicted observations reported in the literature and indicated that the Kangaroo Island
352 megafire was of high severity and burned BNM sites at high intensity. Furthermore,
353 significant differences in soil nutrient levels and ratios, pH, and microbial communities of
354 cleared and grazed pasture (BM) plots compared to BNM plots exemplified the ability of land
355 management practices to impact post-fire outcomes. These changes in soil properties are
356 intimately linked to vegetation responses post-fire and have implications for the post-
357 disturbance recovery of BNM and BM sites.

358 *4.1 Bushfire impacts on soil properties*

359 The Kangaroo Island megafire caused the complete combustion of vegetation at BNM plots,
360 resulting in decreased TC, TN, and SWR and significantly increased pH. These trends
361 differed from typical post-fire outcomes from other studies (Christensen and Abbott, 1989;
362 Hopmans et al., 2005; Krishnaraj et al., 2016), and indicated that the 2019-2020 fire burned at
363 high severity across the study site. Low severity fire has been shown to increase soil carbon
364 levels through the deposition of charcoal, and high severity fires that scorch the leaf canopy
365 deposit nutrient-rich leaf litter, increasing post-fire soil nitrogen and phosphorous levels
366 (Christensen and Abbott, 1989; Krishnaraj et al., 2016). However, we observed a decrease in
367 both TN and TC due to fire (Fig. 2). This may be explained by the complete combustion of
368 aboveground organic matter and tree canopy that occurred, thus preventing post-fire nutrient
369 deposition (Eidenshink et al., 2007; Keeley, 2009; Knox and Clarke, 2016). Furthermore, in
370 BNM plots, the pH changed from 4.44 ± 0.08 to 6.20 ± 0.06 . This is consistent with the
371 change in pH reported by Tomkins et al. (1991), in which a high severity fire resulting from

372 300 tonnes of fuel per acre caused pH to rise from an average of 4.65 to 6.4 in the first two
373 centimetres of soil. However, the pH change in BNM plots reached the depth of 5cm,
374 implying the fire likely burned at higher severity in BNM plots than the fire in Tomkins et al.
375 (1991). Given its level of severity, the fire at BNM plots may have negatively affected native
376 vegetation by causing low carbon and nitrogen availability, iron insolubility due to high pH,
377 seed mortality, and tree kill (Etchells et al., 2020; Peverill et al., 1999; Rovira et al., 2004).

378 Fire also caused SWR to decrease in BNM plots. A unique feature of dry sclerophyll
379 woodland soils is that they are known to be water repellent as a product of the quality and
380 quantity of SOM present (Neary et al., 2008; Walden et al., 2015). For example, Crockford et
381 al. (1991) observed consistent high SWR in dry sclerophyll woodland in the Yass River
382 Basin of south-eastern Australia from 1981 to 1984 and across five additional dry sclerophyll
383 forests in 1979 and 1980. The SWR typical in dry sclerophyll woodland can be due to a thick
384 litter and SOM layer, acidity in soil, and the presence of fungal mycelium (Crockford et al.,
385 1991; Lozano et al., 2013; Neary et al., 2008).

386 Fire has distinct impacts on SWR that depend on fire severity metrics, biome and climate
387 (Bodí et al., 2014; Debano, 2000; Martins et al., 2020). For example, moderate to medium
388 severity fires are known to increase SWR in the topsoil by adding partially combusted
389 organic matter back into the soil (Pereira et al., 2019), and DeBano et al. (1976) showed that
390 fire can intensify SWR after only a 5-minute experimental burn using pine litter on sand.
391 Contrastingly, fire has been shown to reduce SWR caused by Eucalyptus species. For
392 example, Martins et al. (2020) reported a decrease in SWR after only a moderate severity
393 wildfire in a Portuguese eucalypt forest. Furthermore, Faria et al. (2015) reported that in
394 another eucalypt stand in Portugal, fire reduced major components of the hydrophobic soil
395 free lipid fraction, i.e., terpenes, terpenoids and steroids, by 50%, and Arcenegui et al. (2019)

396 explained that alkaline conditions, such as those created by fire, discourage SWR due to
397 increased solubility of hydrophobic compounds. Due to the dry sclerophyll vegetation type,
398 the high severity of the fire that occurred in BNM plots, and the fire-induced rise in pH, this
399 fire event reduced SWR, which may have benefited post-fire regeneration (Madsen et al.,
400 2012). However, not much post-fire vegetation regrowth was observed on the forest floor of
401 BNM sites 6-months post-fire (Fig. 1).

402 In addition to physicochemical properties, microbial community composition and diversity
403 and their response to fire were of interest. Fire causes microbial cell death at soil
404 temperatures as low as 60°C but can also act as a stressor to surviving microbes, stimulating
405 microbial reproduction below the soil surface (Hart et al., 2005). In consequence, microbial
406 community composition is sensitive to disturbance and informative of the soil's state of
407 recovery after disturbance (Ammitzboll et al., 2021; Muñoz-Rojas and Bárcenas-Moreno,
408 2019). Most observed differences in the bacterial community were consistent with the
409 literature. For instance, Weber et al. (2014) observed that a wildfire significantly increased
410 the abundance of Firmicutes and Bacteroidetes and decreased Acidobacteria abundance in
411 ponderosa pine and mixed conifer forests. Although these vegetation types differ from the dry
412 sclerophyll woodland that was the focus of this study, these observations from Weber et al.
413 (2014) are consistent with our results. Firmicutes have been shown to proliferate after fire
414 disturbance (Ferrenberg et al., 2013; Weber et al., 2014). Furthermore, Bacteroidetes have
415 been positively correlated and Acidobacteria have been negatively correlated with increased
416 carbon mineralization (Fierer et al., 2007; Weber et al., 2014). Thus, the changes observed in
417 these phyla due to fire may have increased carbon mineralization, improving nutrient
418 availability and promoting vegetation growth (Al-Maliki and Ebreesum, 2020).

419 Fire also decreased the RA of Actinobacteria, but this observation is not consistent with the
420 literature. Across multiple studies in ecosystems ranging from the boreal and temperate
421 forests of China to multiple variable landscape across the United Kingdom, Actinobacteria
422 were positively correlated with pH (Griffiths et al., 2011; Shen et al., 2013; Xiang et al.,
423 2014). However, while pH increased in BNM plots due to fire, Actinobacteria abundance
424 decreased. Furthermore, Xiang et al. (2014) observed no change to Actinobacteria abundance
425 after both low and high intensity fire in boreal forests of China, and in pine forests of China,
426 medium and high severity wildfire caused Actinobacteria abundance to increase (Li et al.,
427 2019). Our results imply that there is another factor, besides pH, responsible for
428 Actinobacteria abundance. In addition to its correlation to pH, Xiang et al. (2014) showed
429 that Actinobacteria abundance is positively correlated with soil nitrogen. Thus, the post-fire
430 decrease in TN may have contributed to the observed decrease in Actinobacteria in BNM
431 plots.

432 Fire also caused changes in the community composition of fungi (Fig. 4), which in alignment
433 with the literature, were more drastic than fire-induced changes to bacterial communities
434 (Borgogni et al., 2019a). After fire, changes in the RA of known ECM fungi indicated a
435 reduction in the diversity of ECM fungi (Brundrett, 2008; Spatafora et al., 2017). In
436 consequence, fire may have reduced soil functionality by lessening the number of symbiotic
437 relationships possible between fungi and vegetation (Tommerup and Bougher 2000). The
438 dominant phylum in dry sclerophyll woodland plots also changed from Basidiomycota to
439 Ascomycota and the dominant groups of Basidiomycota changed from fleshy mushroom
440 producing fungi to yeasts. Both of these changes have been observed in the literature as a
441 consequence of fire (Ammitzboll et al., 2021; Pérez-Izquierdo et al., 2021). Furthermore, the
442 dominant group of fungi changed from primarily sexually reproducing ECM fungi,
443 Basidiomycota Agaricomycetes, to the asexually reproducing ECM fungi, Ascomycota

444 Eurotiomycetes Eurotiales. This shift in fungal reproductive mode could indicate a fire-
445 induced selection against sexual reproduction in fungi.

446 Microbial diversity is another biological property associated with soil function and has been
447 used to assess the impact of disturbances such as fire (Ammitzboll et al., 2021; Muñoz-Rojas
448 and Bárcenas-Moreno, 2019; Rodríguez et al., 2017). The diversity of bacterial communities
449 increased due to fire in BNM plots, but there was no change in the diversity of soil eukaryote
450 communities. Many studies have observed a decrease in the diversity of bacteria and fungi
451 within the first few months post-fire (Ammitzboll et al., 2021; Ferrenberg et al., 2013; Sáenz
452 de Miera et al., 2020; Tian et al., 2021). Additionally, Rodríguez et al. (2017) observed that a
453 high severity fire in the Mediterranean forests of Spain caused significantly higher bacterial
454 diversity in burnt compared to unburnt plots, 1 year post-fire. These findings suggest that
455 high severity fire can cause a short-term increase in bacterial diversity, as observed here,
456 despite an initial decline in abundance and diversity, which is commonly reported in the
457 literature.

458 *4.2 Historical land use impacts on soil properties*

459 The interactive effects of fire and management resulted in significantly different post-fire
460 conditions in historically grazed pastures (BM) than adjacent dry sclerophyll woodland
461 impacted by the same fire (BNM). These differences can be contributed to management-
462 induced changes to pre-fire soil and vegetation conditions and dependent fire dynamics (Bodí
463 et al., 2014; Pereira et al., 2019; Shakesby and Doerr, 2006). Many of the post-fire
464 differences in BM compared to BNM plots are consistent with the known impacts of clearing
465 and grazing on soil conditions. McGregor et al. (2017) showed that clearing and grazing can
466 cause an increase in nitrogen and weed content, reduce C/N, and modify SWR and microbial
467 communities, as were observed in BM plots when compared to BNM plots. Furthermore, the
468 optimal C/N for native vegetation in mallee or dry sclerophyll woodland is reported to be 20-

469 30, which is consistent with values observed in BNM plots, while in BM plots, we observed a
470 C/N of 14.92 ± 0.51 , which is consistent with grass and shrublands (Bui and Henderson,
471 2013; Neave and Raison, 1999). The raised TN and reduced C/N in BM plots are likely
472 contributors to the weeds that dominate the vegetation of BM plots (McGregor et al., 2017).
473 In consequence, the near 100% groundcover observed 6-months post-fire in BM plots will
474 provide a post-fire protective effect against soil erosion and nutrient run-off, thus preserving
475 soil nutrient content (Badía et al., 2011; Neary, 2009; van Leeuwen et al., 2019). However,
476 the weeds, e.g., *Romulea* spp., *Medicago* spp. and *Arctotheca calendula*, may outcompete
477 native vegetation and stifle young tree and shrub growth, hindering post-fire recovery of dry
478 sclerophyll woodland in BM plots (Davies et al., 2013; McGregor et al., 2017; Yates and
479 Hobbs, 1997).

480 The lack of trees and shrub understorey in pastures prior to the fire event may have reduced
481 the BM plots' contribution to copious ecosystem services provided by diverse vegetation and
482 trees, including food and habitat, water availability and air filtration, microclimate
483 stabilization, and climate disaster mitigation by carbon fixation (Griscom et al., 2017; Staal et
484 al., 2020; Vallejo et al., 2004). However, at the time of the fire event, these changes to
485 vegetation amounted to a smaller pre-fire fuel load, which would have caused a lower fire
486 severity and less severe impacts on soil properties in BM compared to BNM plots (Neary,
487 2009; Tomkins et al., 1991). In consequence, management likely reduced some of the
488 extreme impacts of this bushfire, imposing a protective effect on the present vegetation and
489 soil properties of BM plots. This protective effect would support higher nutrient levels, lower
490 pH, and higher SWR, and may also counteract impacts on microbial communities. Land
491 management did in-fact counteract fire-impacts on nutrient levels and pH and may have
492 reduced the effect of fire on SWR, but soil microbial community composition and diversity
493 indicate further contribution of land management to soil function.

494 We observed a higher microbial diversity in both bacterial and soil eukaryote communities of
495 BM plots compared to BNM plots, indicating a broader range of microbial species and/or a
496 more even RA of all species present to perform soil functions in BM plots (Ammitzboll et al.,
497 2021; Fierer et al., 2013; Rodríguez et al., 2017). Soil biodiversity contributes to resilience to
498 disturbance and ecosystem productivity, and so increased microbial diversity and evenness
499 are positive indications of functional soil (Borgogni et al., 2019b; D'Ascoli et al., 2005;
500 Rodríguez et al., 2017). However, the modified microbial community compositions in BM
501 plots will have consequences on the functions carried out by the microbial communities and
502 the symbiotic relationships present between microbes and vegetation. Changes in vegetation
503 and consequent differences in organic matter inputs are common contributors to differences
504 in fungal communities, and thus, it is not surprising that our results indicate that clearing and
505 grazing had a significant impact on fungal community composition.

506 Another marked change we observed was a decrease in the total relative abundance of known
507 ECM fungi in BM sites due to management (Brundrett, 2008; Tedersoo et al., 2010). ECM
508 fungi are known to form symbiotic relationships with and are responsible for providing
509 nutrients to Eucalyptus species, promoting seedling establishment and recovery (Pérez-
510 Izquierdo et al., 2021; Tommerup and Bougher, 2000). Thus, reduced abundance of ECM
511 fungi likely impacted post-fire recovery of native vegetation in BM plots. As ECM fungi are
512 known to be negatively impacted by higher nitrogen content (Tommerup and Bougher, 2000),
513 the raised TN in BM plots may have contributed to this decrease in ECM fungi.

514 Management-induced alterations to vegetation composition and consequent changes to soil
515 inputs are also known to drive changes in microbial composition (Hart et al., 2005). In
516 consequence, the decrease in the RA of ECM fungi in BM plots may pose a challenge for the
517 re-establishment of Eucalyptus trees in these pastures. Furthermore, the observed changes in
518 TC, C/N, weed content and SWR are known to hinder natural vegetation recovery in dry

519 sclerophyll woodland, meaning that active restoration will likely be required to revegetate
520 BM plots with native woodland species (McGregor et al., 2017).

521 *4.3 Limitations and Future Applications*

522 Further monitoring of post-fire soil properties of these sites and vegetative surveys assessing
523 recovery of aboveground vegetation would provide valuable insights to continue this work.

524 Furthermore, an assessment of unburnt versus burnt pastureland would help elucidate the
525 impacts of fire on pastureland. The direct measurement of soil properties proved valuable for
526 the assessment of fire and land use impacts on soil function and may also be of use to assess
527 the impacts of other disturbances on soil function, including mining, floods, and other
528 combinations of land use change and natural disasters associated with climate change. One
529 major limitation of this approach is the area of land one can assess in a reasonable amount of
530 time. Miesel et al. (2018) provides an example of how future studies may combine the direct
531 measurement of soil properties with remote sensing, amplifying the power of this approach to
532 monitor post-fire soil function and recovery.

533 **5. Conclusions**

534 Our results show that both fire and historical clearing and grazing can cause significant shifts
535 in post-fire soil properties. The bushfire studied here caused atypical impacts on soils,
536 including a decrease in soil nutrients and diversity of ECM fungi in burnt dry sclerophyll
537 woodland. Furthermore, in contradiction with our hypothesis, prior management may have
538 reduced the severity of the fire in BM plots. However, the observed reduction in C/N and
539 changes to the microbial community composition imply that management modified the
540 relationship between fire and post-fire regeneration of native dry sclerophyll
541 vegetation (Prendergast-Miller et al., 2017). This study shows the importance of considering
542 previous land management when assessing fire outcomes. Future studies may strengthen
543 these findings by including unburnt managed sites, providing further information of pre-fire

544 conditions and the impact of management on BM sites. Furthermore, this study demonstrates
545 that measurements of both soil physicochemical and biological properties provide valuable
546 insights into the impacts of fire and pre-fire land use on soil. These insights have important
547 implications for the preservation and restoration of native ecosystems in the face of climate
548 change-induced exacerbated fire regimes, expanding land use, and abandonment of
549 agricultural land.

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957 **Appendix A. Supplementary data**

958 **Table S1.** Soil properties by treatment. Values (mean \pm SE, total $n = 12$) and p-values from
 959 contrasts of estimated marginal means of modelled data, $p < 0.05$ (*), $p < 0.01$ (**) and $p <$
 960 0.001 (***). (A) physicochemical soil properties, (B) soil bacteria diversity metrics (16S
 961 rRNA primers), and (C) soil eukaryotes diversity metrics (18S rRNA primers). UNM:
 962 unburnt non-managed ($n = 4$); BNM: burnt non-managed ($n = 4$); BM: burnt managed ($n =$
 963 4). AC: potassium permanganate soluble organic carbon (mg/kg of soil); TC: total carbon
 964 (%); TN: total nitrogen (%); pH: pH; EC: electrical conductivity ($\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$); SWR: soil water
 965 repellency (s); S: richness; H: Shannon's entropy; e^H : the natural exponential of Shannon's
 966 entropy; J: Pielou's evenness; D^{-1} : inverse Simpson's diversity; E_D : Simpson's evenness.

(A) Soil Property	Treatment				Treatment			
	UNM	v.	BNM	<i>p</i>	BNM	v.	BM	<i>p</i>
AC	553.76 \pm 23.45		596.69 \pm 21.88	0.268	596.69 \pm 21.88		632.02 \pm 36.97	0.697
TC	18.85 \pm 2.43		3.35 \pm 0.15	0.152	3.35 \pm 0.15		5.86 \pm 0.55	0.782
TN	0.67 \pm 0.08		0.13 \pm 0.01	<0.001***	0.13 \pm 0.01		0.39 \pm 0.04	0.406
C/N	28.43 \pm 0.48		26.60 \pm 1.22	0.306	26.60 \pm 1.22		14.92 \pm 0.51	<0.001***
pH	4.44 \pm 0.08		6.20 \pm 0.06	<0.001***	6.20 \pm 0.06		5.40 \pm 0.08	<0.001***
EC	120.7 \pm 10.5		92.7 \pm 6.2	<0.001***	92.7 \pm 6.2		88.3 \pm 4.9	0.075
SWR	3463 \pm 122		55 \pm 8	<0.001***	55 \pm 8		1064 \pm 209	0.292
(B) Soil Property	Treatment				Treatment			
	UNM	v.	BNM	<i>p</i>	BNM	v.	BM	<i>p</i>
S	1925 \pm 58		2119 \pm 67	0.033*	2119 \pm 67		2653 \pm 49	<0.001***
H	5.88 \pm 0.06		6.27 \pm 0.06	<0.001***	6.27 \pm 0.06		6.65 \pm 0.04	<0.001***
e^H	362.98 \pm 21.08		536.92 \pm 30.81	<0.001***	536.92 \pm 30.81		776.14 \pm 31.10	<0.001***
J	0.78 \pm 0.00		0.82 \pm 0.00	<0.001***	0.82 \pm 0.00		0.84 \pm 0.00	0.008**
D^{-1}	76.12 \pm 3.22		148.04 \pm 13.30	0.01*	148.04 \pm 13.30		120.33 \pm 10.52	0.277
E_D	0.04 \pm 0.00		0.07 \pm 0.01	0.014*	0.07 \pm 0.01		0.05 \pm 0.00	0.02*
(C) Soil Property	Treatment				Treatment			
	UNM	v.	BNM	<i>p</i>	BNM	v.	BM	<i>p</i>
S	1111 \pm 71		912 \pm 75	0.138	912 \pm 75		1764 \pm 47	<0.001***
H	3.44 \pm 0.13		3.50 \pm 0.20	0.927	3.50 \pm 0.20		4.34 \pm 0.09	0.003**
e^H	34.35 \pm 5.18		40.35 \pm 8.44	0.668	40.35 \pm 8.44		80.65 \pm 8.14	0.002**
J	0.49 \pm 0.01		0.51 \pm 0.02	0.555	0.51 \pm 0.02		0.58 \pm 0.01	0.027*
D^{-1}	9.62 \pm 0.97		10.23 \pm 2.39	0.843	10.23 \pm 2.39		15.02 \pm 2.07	0.128
E_D	0.01 \pm 0.00		0.01 \pm 0.00	0.286	0.01 \pm 0.00		0.01 \pm 0.00	0.275

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968	(1) $K_e = mx + b$ (mole \cdot KMnO ₄ /L \cdot KMnO ₄)	982	K_e = ending molarity of KMnO ₄ (mole/L)
969		983	m = slope of standard curve
970		984	x = absorbance at 550nm
971		985	$b = y -$ intercept of standard curve
972	(2) $K_c = K_s - K_e$ (moles \cdot KMnO ₄ /L \cdot KMnO ₄)	986	K_c = consumed KMnO ₄ (moles/L)
973		987	K_s = starting molarity of KMnO ₄ (mole/L)
974	(3) $AC = R_c \cdot K_v \cdot K_c$ (mg \cdot C)	988	AC = Active Carbon (mg)
975		989	R_c = Conversion rate: 9000 mg of active
976		990	carbon per mole of KMnO ₄ consumed
977		991	(Blair et al., 1995)
978		992	K_v = starting volume of KMnO ₄ solution (L)
979	(4) $[AC] = AC/S_m$ (mg \cdot C/kg \cdot soil)	993	$[AC]$ = Concentration of active carbon (mg/kg)
980	$[AC] = R_c \cdot K_v \cdot (K_s - mx + b)/S_m$	994	S_m = Soil mass (kg)
981	$[AC] = [9000 \cdot 0.02 \cdot (0.02 - mx + b)]/0.005$		

995 **Figure S1.** Labile active carbon calculations. Equations used to convert absorbance (nm) to
 996 carbon (mg/kg of soil) are presented on the left; (1) The final remaining molarity of KMnO₄,
 997 (2) the molarity of KMnO₄ consumed during the reaction, (3) the total mass of active carbon
 998 (mg) consumed during the reaction, and (4) the mass of active carbon (mg) consumed during
 999 the reaction per kilogram of soil, which equals the concentration of active carbon (mg/kg)
 1000 present in the soil sample. The meaning of each variable is listed on the right. These
 1001 equations depend on values derived from a calibration curve of KMnO₄ solution and the
 1002 conversion ratio of 0.75mM, or 9mg of C, per 1mM of KMnO₄ consumed (Blair et al., 1995).

1004 **Figure S2.** Relative abundance of soil eukaryote communities. Relative abundance of all 18S
1005 rRNA gene sequence reads (soil eukaryote taxa at the class level) versus treatment and plot
1006 site. UNM: unburnt non-managed plots; BNM: burnt non-managed plots; BM: burnt
1007 managed plots. Unassigned: OTUs that could not be assigned to a taxon; Other: the rarest
1008 assigned OTUs adding up to $\leq 5\%$ of all OTU reads.